

Synchronous Collaborative Music Lessons and their digital materiality

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ABSTRACT

It is increasingly acknowledged that digital artifacts of any kind may be crafted from a variety of *materials* that include programming languages, notations, scripts, code generators, etc. As these materials are digital natives, they are distinctly different from conventional instruments. In an attempt to grasp their full potential and to gain insights into what constitutes their materiality, researchers have recently engaged in useful argumentation about the properties of such digital materials. Using an evolving case study on Synchronous Collaborative Music Lessons (SCMLs), we seek to contribute to this argumentation by showcasing how designated digital materials and their transformative capacity can re-organize the conduct of a jazz improvisation music lesson.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years several scientific and research communities have advocated the call for a ‘material turn’ in the design of interactive computer-based systems [1][2] as well as the compelling need for understanding properties of digital materials and immaterial artifacts [9][10][11][12] that shape design-oriented decisions and practices. This paper rests on these scholarships and attempts to (a) establish a vocabulary that guides design inquiries towards an appreciation of the role of digital materials and (b) assess the value of this vocabulary by elaborating on a particular virtual work setting – that of Synchronous Collaborative Music Lessons (SCMLs).

Before engaging with our main line of argumentation, it is perhaps appropriate to justify what we mean by SCMLs. In general, SCMLs are shared co-engagements between two or more human collaborators with the aim of learning music. This is achieved by entangling individual performative capacity (understanding symbolic forms of music, competence in using a musical instrument, etc.) with designated material settings across sites (personal versus shared space, specific instrument, surroundings, temporal sequence of events, etc.). Noticeably,

these entanglements may result in improving, augmenting or even creating new opportunities for working with music (e.g., co-creating, improvising or experimenting with music). Another key feature of SCMLs is their material context. This is interesting and challenging because the physical space where musicians operate (i.e., private or shared physical space, local instruments) is intertwined with the digital space (i.e., computing infrastructure, representations, tools and digital equipment). Again, such intertwining creates new opportunities for action since digital representations of music are continuously re-aligning the way in which music is articulated. It is therefore argued that SCMLs constitute a case illustrating how an assemblage of embedded agencies established through sensory-based media migrates to a new digital assemblage which is amenable to virtual work.

In terms of materialities, SCMLs in the broader sense of the term may engage computational embodiments of music-specific artifacts such as visual symbols (i.e., symbolic notation), sound (that may stand for certain visual symbols), human gestures on musical instruments, as well as digital infrastructure (i.e., cloud settings, desktop, WWW, mobile, digital services such as file- or photo-sharing applications, etc.). The intrinsic ways in which these artifacts are implicated in practice, time after time, justify the claim that SCMLs possess malleable and emergent digital materiality. As an example, let us consider a hypothetical scenario where gestures of a digital music instrument (e.g., messages of the MIDI protocol) are rendered as an audio file as well as an SVG image, i.e., an engraving of a score. It is worth noticing that although there are interdependencies between these materials, the desired equivalence is usually impossible, as different materials have been designed to reveal different music qualities. For instance, rendering a MIDI file to audio discards expressive deviations intentionally introduced by performers. Furthermore, converting one symbolic format to another is usually not a reversible process. Indeed, rendering a MIDI representation of a musical piece will usually produce a different SVG image than rendering the same piece from a MusicXML or Humdrum file, especially in the presence of multiple voices/instruments.

From the above it becomes evident that under the term ‘material’ we are considering not only the digital artifacts per se, but also their affordances and the ways in which these affordances are configured by non-human actors, such as computational embodiments for capturing, rendering and manipulating sound and / or graphics as well as dedicated algorithms for music

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transcription, score following, computer accompaniment and so on.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. The next section motivates the present work by establishing links with relevant scholarships. Then, an attempt is made to distill key constructs and establish a conceptual scaffold as a guide to designing a system that allows SCML. This scaffold forms the baseline for a designated configuration of digital artifacts leading to an experimental prototype for collaborative SCMLs with a malleable digital materiality. The paper is concluded with an outline of implications and ongoing and future research.

2. RELATED WORK

While the present research is inspired by the evolving traditions in HCI and CSCW, it rests on a variety of scholarships from which materiality builds its argument. This section attempts a brief overview of some of the most prominent works.

2.1 The materiality of digital artifacts

For physical objects such as buildings, chairs and household devices, materiality coins the physical ‘matter’ out of which these objects are constructed. Thus, it implies some form of tangibility of constructions with a physical substance that exists within specific sites. Recently, research works on HCI [5][8][10][16], CSCW [7], information systems [1][11] and ubiquitous computing [12][13] have been critical of this view calling for a ‘material turn’ in perspective [10][12][16]. The ‘material turn’ at least in part has been motivated by our limited understanding of the properties of digital materials. For instance, it is hard to classify and anchor using a common set of properties, genres of digital materials such as 2D / 3D visualizations and simulations [6], various media [2] including digital music [3][11], radio communications [8], but also programming language code (from which interactive artifacts are made) [14], digital services [15][20] and computational composites [16][19].

Another constituency of the ‘material turn’ relates to the repertoire of methods recruited by designers. Ideally, such methods should engage designers in ‘conversation’ with materials that ‘talk back’ to reveal emergent properties and opportunities [9]. For example, although genres of digital artifacts such as web mashups [15] may not be approached through similar craft design practices as those reported in [16] and [18], in both cases the resulting digital artifacts possess common properties i.e., they are fluid due to changes taking place not only in the surrounding environment but also from within.

Due to these complications, it has been argued that for digital artifacts materiality as ‘matter’ is both problematic and questionable [6]. As a result, the term digital materiality has been introduced [6][10][13] to depict an emerging research strand seeking to provide insights to material aspects of digital artifacts as experienced by end users and digital materials as crafted by designers.

Our current effort is motivated by a design-oriented commitment to understand not only the properties of digital materials as these materials become embedded into different technological regimes but also how the selection of digital materials blurs different digital materialities. Our commitment is distinct in focus as it emphasizes the re-configurability of digital materials such as software which renders digital artifacts malleable and capable of spanning (multiple) digital spaces (ranging from different cloud infrastructures, digital services such as file- or photo-sharing

applications, etc.) and material contexts (i.e., desktop, WWW, mobile). Equally important for our analysis are the design qualities embedded in the various material settings (i.e., toolkit abstractions, traceability, openness, etc.) but also the connecting glue (i.e., code fragments, established protocols and APIs) that ascribe a transformative capacity to digital artifacts and determine how they are used, mobilized, traced, reflected upon and implicated in practice. Arguably, such an agenda is not only timely (see for example recent works in CSCW and HCI venues [7][21]), but also novel in the sense that it re-aligns our perspective on fundamental questions about the design of technology.

2.2 Digital materiality and representation

From the variety of issues that may be relevant to an exploratory treatment of digital materiality, one stands out prominently and constitutes the primary focus in the present work; that is representation. Representation as a concept may be approached from several angles. Firstly, in semiotic terms it may be conceived as signifier for a variety of signified entities, including humans, physical objects but also intangible processes or (i.e., phenomena known to exist and perform certain function such as compilation, coding/decoding data or synchronizing in file sharing services, etc.). Representations are also the ‘matter’ ascribing material agency to digital technologies and/or invoking social agency in a designated context. It should be clearly noted that representation as ‘matter’ possesses no performative capacity. However, when embedded in media types (i.e., traditional or computer-reliant), it inherits properties of these media which determine possibilities for action and regimes of virtual work [6].

It can be easily ascertained that in any non-trivial scenarios of virtual work several representations can become blurred and interwoven within the same or across different systems to amplify the execution of routines. For our purposes, a human routine may entail operating on a representation A (i.e., a visual score) which can be aligned or configured with another representation B such as a MIDI file standing for or substituting a distant peer (who is operating with representation B) and both may then facilitate a digital assemblage that enables work through (i.e., remote control of a distant setting) or within (i.e., virtual work by a music ensemble in the absence of a peer) representations.

2.3 Transformative capacity

This brings to the surface an important property of digital artifacts, namely their transformative capacity. As transformative capacity, we define the capability of certain digital artefacts to re-organize entire organizational routines on new premises – thus introducing a certain degree of instability in the prevalent set of activities – until the artefact is either rejected or institutionalized. In its simplest form transformative capacity manifests itself as the re-configuration of activities in a source domain (i.e., clicks, or likes in a system, a blog or a web site) to symbols in a target domain (i.e., 2D/3D visualization, GUI dialogue) in such ways so as to invoke human intentionalities not viable through the source domain representation. In a similar vein, single sign-on services transform user profiles into an emergent portable representation that allow their physical referents to cross (multiple) digital boundaries.

Nonetheless, transformative capacity can also be framed at the level of entire systems and services. For instance, the Twitter micro-blogging service transforms the meaning potential of a typographic convention, the hashtag, so as to upscale the call to affiliate with values expressed in tweets as well as to render

language searchable [4]. Moreover, Twitter data as retained and exposed by its APIs can be processed to reveal enacted social accomplishments such as imagined communities. In this sense Twitter embodies transformative capacity as most of the digital material retained within Twitter is codified in a certain format / representation, while through the API, it can be retooled or transformed into another (i.e., XML or JSON format) to invoke (new) human intentionalities. Other examples where transformative capacity reveals its face include Web crawlers [23], social widgets and mashups [24]. Noticeably they all present cases of non-human actors which through appropriate configurations make visible certain (traditionally hidden or absent) properties of a technology (i.e., digital trace data management functions).

From the above it follows that transformative capacity is a relative construct, incapable of absolute or quantitative measurement. It can only be determined by intrinsic properties of digital representations such as non-functional qualities and the (new) range of human intentionalities invoked. It may also be claimed that transformative capacity is 'injectable' into digital artifacts using code, but it is only enacted in use, either when humans perform through the technology or when the technology itself is activated by another technology (by means of recruiting a contracting protocol such as an API).

3. MUSICOLAB LESSONS

In this section we present the current state of developments towards SCMLs as conceived in the context of an on-going research and development project (see Acknowledgement). We will briefly highlight a reference scenario and then engage with the main arguments unfolding the (digital) materiality of SCMLs.

3.1 Reference scenario

For purposes of illustration, we refer to a jazz improvisation learning scenario, in which three connected musicians negotiate by collectively adapting a pre-existing score of a jazz trio comprising three music parts: a piano, a drums and a double bass part. We envisage such a lesson as a fully computer-supported collaborative co-engagement between peers with different roles

such as teachers, learners or audience. Although such a lesson may entail individual and / or asynchronous tasks (i.e., announcement of homework by teachers, sharing of learning materials, private study by learners, uploads of submissions, email exchanges, etc.) it also comprises synchronous activities which are carried out by peers (with designated access rights) as purely virtual work. These activities are spread across two constituencies, namely communication and collaborative work on a shared artifact (i.e., a shared music score).

SCMLs of the type presented above are interesting and challenging endeavors for several reasons. Firstly, they intertwine individual performative capacity (understanding symbolic forms of music, competence in using a musical instrument, etc.) with designated material settings across sites (personal versus shared space, specific instrument, surroundings, temporal sequence of events, etc.) Such entanglements may result in improving, augmenting or even creating new opportunities for working with music (e.g., co-creating, improvising or experimenting with music).

Secondly, the materiality of SCMLs poses new challenges as the physical space where musicians operate (i.e., private or shared physical space, local instruments) is intertwined with the digital space (i.e., computing infrastructure, representations, tools and digital equipment). Such intertwining creates new opportunities for action since digital representations of music are continuously re-aligning the way in which music is articulated. For example, music may be constructed using a variety of digital notations, visualizations, instruments, and toolsets, while due to the increasingly participatory culture, it is also shared and consumed in ways not viable in earlier regimes (i.e., use of macroscopic metadata). Consequently, our case study is ideally suited for creative designs as it unfolds how an assemblage of embedded agencies established through sensory-based media migrates to a new digital assemblage which is amenable to virtual work.

3.2 The research prototype

A snapshot of our lesson is depicted in Figure 1. The top part of the Figure depicts the Conferencing Component, while the bottom part depicts the shared Notation Editor.

Figure 1 : SCML with three participants

Viewer (VHV)⁵ is an online digital music editor and interactive notation rendering interface for Humdrum files capable of satisfying the established requirements. Specifically, VHV creates a SVG graphical representation of the music as represented in `**kern`, while also offering some basic mouse-based direct manipulation facilities. However, VHV is also restricted by certain limitations. For our SCML and especially music composition scenarios, it's often necessary for a participant (usually the instructor) to highlight a particular area of the music score (e.g., a measure, a chord or an arbitrary range of notes) in order to initiate a discussion with their co-participants. Furthermore, collaborative software usually allows the addition of comments through functionality provided by the utilized toolset (think of commenting in Google Docs), which correlates a selected area with a text message. VHV does not provide such functionality and, therefore, had to be expanded in order to support mechanisms such as multiple note selection via rubber banding and commenting for already selected objects/elements directly on the SVG graphical representation.

4.1.4 Yjs for real-time music notation editing

The final material addresses issues of real-time music-score editing (and collaboration) between remote users. It should be noted that the techniques added to VHV to enrich its basic interaction affordances (see earlier description) do not scale up to synchronous collaboration or its properties. In other words, VHV does not make provisions for managing remote collaboration between participants. For this purpose, the Yjs framework⁶ is recruited to handle all aspects of real-time music score editing, activity awareness, remote control, conflict resolution, etc.

Yjs is a high-performance shared editing framework for building collaborative applications that sync automatically [25]. It is based on research work on Conflict-free Replicated Data Types (CRDTs) [26]. In this model, each client maintains a replica of the shared state, applies modifications locally which are then broadcast to remote participants so that they can update the state of their own replicas while potential conflicts are resolved automatically. At present, Yjs has been used to synch replicas of the `**kern` instance rendered through the augmented VHV as well as the associated collaborative practices.

In the current implementation this is facilitated by binding the Humdrum text editor included in VHV with Yjs' shared data structure for representing text (`Y.Text`). As a result, both direct and indirect modifications applied to the shared referent music object through either manipulating text represented in `**kern` or the SVG graphical representation of the VHV music score are applied and then broadcast to other participants, while ensuring that every participant will eventually have the same state of the shared object. Moreover, information regarding activity awareness produced by the augmented version of VHV is passed to Yjs and by utilizing the awareness API, this is broadcast to remote participants.

With regards to syncing, Yjs relies on a high-level protocol which constitutes a simple message exchange sequence for the connected clients. Clients either send their local state or reply to remote clients with the state segment that they are missing in an efficient manner. The awareness API is utilized to efficiently construct

update messages with information about activity awareness (peer actions at a given moment) and social presence (who is connected) which are not part of the main shared data structure. In addition, network connectors are part of the Yjs ecosystem which internally implement the aforementioned protocols/APIs in order to connect Yjs with well-established network protocols (e.g., WebSocket or WebRTC).

4.2 Configuration of materials

Having presented the list of digital materials comprising the MusiCoLab's SCMLs, it would be appropriate to examine the way in which these materials are configured (i.e., how they are 'glued' together) to form a digital composite. Typically, configuration tactics stem from the (lack of) affordances of certain materials. Specifically, the `**kern` notation although based on text and thus abstract enough, lacks intuition especially for certain user profiles. VHV offers a solution by undertaking an automatic *transcription* of text (`**kern`) into symbols/score (SVG) which is arguably more intuitive for musicians. In a similar vein, VHV is poor in provisions for direct manipulation of symbols in a score. This limitation creates the need for *augmenting* VHV to allow direct manipulation of notes, multiple note selection, etc.

It is worth noticing that such an *augmentation* although useful for editing the score results in capabilities that are not directly mapped to `**kern`. In other words, although working on `**kern` has an immediate effect on VHV and vice versa (suggesting that these two digital materials are *interdependent*), multiple note selection in the augmented VHV does not have a corresponding equivalent in `**kern`. Similarly, VHV has been *integrated* with Yjs to facilitate real-time score editing and collaboration while `**kern`, VHV and Yjs were all *embedded* into Jitsi.

Following this line of thinking it may be argued that lack of affordances of any digital material may justify further developments in designated directions. For instance, current work focuses in *expanding* Jitsi to facilitate *interoperation* between materials so that the current speaker (in Jitsi) may not only share the screen but also operate *through* voice on a remote representation of music on a different material such as VHV.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

A prominent issue in our study of SCMLs is how the material of software affords bindings across representation(s) of music. As pointed out, although the digital score does not allow articulation of certain dynamic properties of music, this limitation is alleviated by *remediating* score to a different representation (i.e., interactions on MIDI piano-roll). Moreover, codifying the object of work using abstract representations (such as XML) allows *retooling* from one form to another, *intertwining* so that operations on certain representation can complement operations on another or even *transforming* across media types as in the case of transcription that renders event-based digital trace data into summative 2D visualizations.

These examples point to the conclusion that software as material imposes constraints, but it also exhibits novel affordances. One such affordance is its transformative capacity, which in the general case, may facilitate complex and challenging tasks such as media alignment, transcription, concatenation, etc. Nonetheless, as in most cases, transformative capacity should be grounded on properties of digital materials and the design practices through which it is acquired. Our current work points to several interesting properties such as augmentation, expansion, abstraction,

⁵ <https://verovio.humdrum.org/>

⁶ <https://github.com/yjs/yjs>

integration, all fostering designated tactics for grounding the notion of transformative capacity of digital materials.

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